

Radiation arrow and missing magnetic monopoles

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Abstract.- *In this paper a new solution for the time-asymmetry of radiation is proposed. The novelty is that the time behaviour of the electromagnetic field is unlinked from the time behaviour of the charge in motion. This has consequences on the number of monopoles required for the symmetry of classic electromagnetism.*

Keywords: Radiation arrow, magnetic monopole, time reversibility, Maxwell's equations.

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1. Introduction

In classic electromagnetism, there is a paradox with the time-asymmetry of radiation: on the one hand, the physical behaviour of radiation is clearly irreversible, (the field propagates from sources to sinks, not the opposite), but Maxwell's equations are theoretically time-reversible, and apparently do not account for the radiation arrow [1]. This mismatch between theory and reality has not yet been conciliated satisfactorily [2-7], and obliges to review the principle on which basis Maxwell's equations are taken as time-reversible.

Formulated by E. Wigner in a fundamental paper in 1932 [8], the exact terminology employed was *reversal of motion*, not *reversal of time* [9]. This means that the electromagnetic field is viewed in purely *mechanistic* terms: its behaviour in time is subordinated to the behaviour of the charge in motion.

This subordination implies a particular way to solve Maxwell's equations with the time backwards. That way consists in reassigning the minus coming from the time backwards to one of the fields, —which conventionally is the magnetic field [10]. So the conventional approach in the textbooks for the time inversion lies in the substitution of \mathbf{B} by $-\mathbf{B}$ in Maxwell's equations, considering the *effect* that a charge moving backwards would produce on the magnetic field. Still, there is another approach by Feynman, which, instead, reassigns the minus coming from the time backwards to the electric field, (i.e., \mathbf{E} is replaced by $-\mathbf{E}$ in Maxwell's equations), now considering the *cause*, i.e., the fact that, for a charge to reverse its motion, it would require a reversed electric field. Both approaches are complementary and self-excluding. This exclusion is the seed of their wrongness: both are possibly right, so none of them can be, since the one's success implies the failure of the other. Correctness is compromised in the dilemma of choosing between cause or effect, indissolubly connected by the time-link we are looking for.

Leaving interpretations aside, if for the time reversal we need to take on board \mathbf{B} by $-\mathbf{B}$ (or \mathbf{E} by $-\mathbf{E}$) in Maxwell's equations, this means that, strictly speaking, we are not solving Maxwell's equations: we are solving Maxwell's equations *plus a condition* in the field. We are therefore *driving* the solution, on the basis of what we think the time reversal might be, —a perception that may be wrong if the time reversal is more extraordinary than expected.—

In either case, Maxwell's equations with the time backwards become identical to the time forwards set, (and their solutions, obviously, too), so the electromagnetic field with the time backwards turns out to be the same as the one with the time forwards, (except for a phase shift), which makes inexplicable why then it is not observed, if it is so real.

These conventional approaches are based on that single principle, —I would rather say a *prejudice*—, which considers matter the prime reality, and the field, secondary (in Wigner's own words [11]). At least we have to concede that there exists another way to focus the problem: to invert the importance of matter and field, and consider matter as the subordinated reality, and the field, the prime one. That is the new approach explored in this paper.

2. Analysis

If matter is not relevant for learning the time behaviour of radiation, we can take it away from the equations, and restrict our analysis to Maxwell's equations *in empty space*. Time running forwards makes the passing of time Δt positive, and running backwards, negative. This has been taken into account with the following notation:

$$\Delta t = \begin{cases} \Delta |t| & \Delta t > 0 \\ -\Delta |t| & \Delta t < 0 \end{cases}$$

For a better comparison, let us write both Maxwell's sets, forwards and backwards, together. In natural units, (the light velocity $c=1$):

t (forwards) \rightarrow	$\leftarrow t$ (backwards)
$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{S}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial t } \quad (1.a)$	$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{S}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{L}}}{\partial t } \quad (2.a)$

$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{S}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{L}}}{\partial t } \quad (1.b)$	$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{S}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial t } \quad (2.b)$

Set (1) in the left is the conventional t -forward, while set (2) in the right is the time-inverted set. In contrast to the conventional approaches, the minus coming from the time

backwards has not been reassigned to any of the fields, but to the surface vector, see figure 1:

$$d\mathbf{S}_R \equiv -d\mathbf{S}_L$$

Equations sets (1) and (2) are of opposite handedness. In (1.a), $d\ell$ is linked to $d\mathbf{S}_R$, so it is conventionally *right*-handed (surface and contour are linked by the right-hand rule). In (1.b), $d\ell$ is linked to $d\mathbf{S}_L$, thus it is *left*-handed (surface and contour are linked by the left-hand rule). Set (2) is the mirrored set (1), if we just allow a change of handedness in the contour-surface link: equations (1.a) and (2.a) are respectively the right and left versions of the same equation, and so are equations (1.b) and (2.b), the left and right versions of the same relation between \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} . Actually the four are all the very same equation, if we just allow the exchange of handedness *Right* \leftrightarrow *Left* and the exchange of fields $\mathbf{E} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{B}$.

This way of writing both sets reveals the hidden symmetry between them. Neither of them seems more special than the other. If we accept no conditions in the fields for set (1), we have no right to deny the same status (condition-free) to set (2), or otherwise, we would be deliberately breaking the symmetry, by favouring one set over the other.

Now both sets are not reversible, against the conventional opinion, but the symmetry between them is *double*: one Maxwell's set becomes the other either if we perform an exchange of *handedness*, (which I have called "**H**-symmetry"), or equivalently, an exchange of *fields* ("**F**-symmetry"). By means of simple algebraic relationships, both transformations can be checked to be equivalent. By direct comparison with the conventional time-forwards wave, the time-backwards wave can be easily obtained (see Appendix I). Obviously, the two waves must reproduce the same double symmetry of the equation sets they come from (see figure 2).

3. Discussion

The time inversion proposed in this paper does not mean any sign flip in the fields, but an *exchange of roles* between the electric and magnetic fields themselves¹:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E} &\xleftarrow{\mathbf{T}} \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} &\xleftarrow{\mathbf{T}} \mathbf{E} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{in natural units})$$

It is possible to justify this result, in comparison with the abovementioned conventional approaches. Basically, the time backwards alters the normal sequence of events, and the cause-effect sequence is also inverted. With time forwards, the electric field (the cause) produces the charge motion, which, at the same time, produces the magnetic field (the effect). With time backwards the opposite is expected: the magnetic field (the effect) “counter-produces” the charge motion reversal (remember, with time backwards), which, at the same time “counter-produces” the electric field (the cause). With this new viewpoint, the exchange of roles between \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} would somehow be justified because, with time backwards, the effect (\mathbf{B}) is *prior* to the cause (\mathbf{E}), and responsible for the charge motion².

4. Implications/Results

This result suggests (or at least, it is compatible with) the existence of “*time borders*”, as extraordinary time points where the electromagnetic field would suffer that extraordinary exchange of roles (not a simple phase shift, without consequences). The borderline between the time forwards and backwards would not be as common as expected, and of course not an arbitrary choice of our timer. Such a time point, in my view, would be more in line with true time borders already predicted in Cosmology, like the Big Bang or the absolute zero temperature. These two points are good time-border candidates, not only for the obvious cosmological reason of End and Beginning of Time they represent, but also for some phenomenology that has been predicted for them.

In relation to the Big Bang, for instance, the time symmetry of the field offers a straightforward explanation for the problem of the missing magnetic monopoles [12-14]. As the time inversion in this paper demands an exchange of roles between \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} at each side of the time border, that implies that, at the time border itself, both fields must be degenerated, $\mathbf{E}=\mathbf{B}$. This degeneration makes it redundant to define two different kinds of monopoles *for a single kind of field* (the degenerated one). If the hypothesis in this paper is correct, there would be only one kind of monopole, whose behaviour as “electric” or “magnetic” would depend on from which side of the time border it is observed. The asymmetry of matter, (represented by the mentioned asymmetry of

¹ The double symmetry should not be mistaken with the conventional electric-magnetic duality, by means of which $\mathbf{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow -\mathbf{E}$, leaving Maxwell’s equations invariant [14]. Being so, the two directions of time are indistinguishable, something which fulminates any hope of hosting time singularities, such as, for instance, the origin of the time arrow. The double symmetry precisely reveals how Maxwell’s equations can discriminate the two directions of time, allowing that possibility.

² This would mean that the electric and magnetic fields would be the temporal mirror of each other.

monopoles) would therefore be linked to the asymmetry of radiation, being both only apparent, consequence of the partial viewpoint from only one side of the time border.

5. Comparison between the conventional approach and this paper's

In classic electromagnetism, the search for symmetry has been conventionally achieved by assuming one single kind of field, (right handed), and two different kinds of charged matter (an electric and a magnetic monopole). This result derives from a specific order of priorities, being matter considered the prime reality and the field, secondary. The magnetic monopoles were not observed physically, but introduced artificially for symmetry reasons. Other symmetrisation attempt is due to Salam, consisting of two types of monopoles (electric and magnetic) and also two types of field (presented as "electric" and "magnetic" photons) [13].

In this paper, the order of priorities has been inverted, (the field is considered the prime reality and matter, secondary), and as a consequence, the symmetry requirements have been also inverted: Now there is need of one single kind of monopole, exchangeable for the two different kinds of field (a right and a left handed versions), see Table I.

This result is compatible with the existence of singularities of Time and with the non-existence of magnetic monopoles in Nature, in agreement with cosmological observations. The existence of time borders such as the Big Bang and the inexistence of magnetic monopoles in Nature are facts against the conventional approach and in favour of this paper's.

Table II shows the comparison between the three symmetrisation models, conventional, Salam's and this paper's.

6. Conclusion

This paper deals with the problem of time inversion in classic Electromagnetism. Once released the conventional hypothesis of subordination of the field to matter, the conclusion is that the electromagnetic field cannot bear the exchange of t by $-t$, unless it suffers a radical exchange of roles between \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} . This transformation would define "time borders", where the electric and magnetic field would be degenerated. Conventional electric phenomena would turn into unconventional magnetic phenomena, and vice versa, at those exceptional time points.

The behaviour of matter in time has been left unsolved in this paper. Not as obvious as a simple backwards motion, it would imply the redefinition of monopoles under the new field, and will have to be inferred from the time-symmetry demanded by the field. It could be a nice topic for the future.

Appendix I

The t-forwards and backwards waves should reproduce the same double symmetry of the equations sets (1) and (2) they come from. If the conventional t-forwards wave is the right-handed triad $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+\}_R$, the t-backwards wave must be the left handed triad $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_-\}_L$, by means of the **H**-symmetry:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \leftarrow \text{t (backwards)} & | & \text{t (forwards)} \rightarrow \\ & \underline{\mathbf{H-symmetry}} & \\ \mathbf{E} \times_L \mathbf{B} & | & \mathbf{E} \times_R \mathbf{B} \end{array}$$

where the cross products, \times_R and \times_L , carry the information of the handedness and have to be distinguished as right- or left (see Appendix II).

Alternatively, t-backward wave can also be expressed, by means of **F**-symmetry, as the right-handed triad $\{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_-\}_R$:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \leftarrow \text{t (backwards)} & | & \text{t (forwards)} \rightarrow \\ & \underline{\mathbf{F-symmetry}} & \\ \mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{E} & | & \mathbf{E} \times_R \mathbf{B} \end{array}$$

Both backward expressions are equivalent, $\mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{E} \equiv \mathbf{E} \times_L \mathbf{B}$, by virtue of the *commutative* property of the cross product for *opposite* handedness (the cross product is *anti commutative* for *same* handedness).

Appendix II

The right cross product \times_R is the conventional cross product \times , based on the right handed system, $\{\mathbf{u}_x, \mathbf{u}_y, \mathbf{u}_{z+}\}$. The left product \times_L is based on the mirror image of the right handed system, $\{\mathbf{u}_x, \mathbf{u}_y, \mathbf{u}_{z-}\}$:

$$\mathbf{A} \times_L \mathbf{B} = \begin{vmatrix} \mathbf{u}_x & \mathbf{u}_y & \mathbf{u}_{z-} \\ a_x & a_y & a_{z-} \\ b_x & b_y & b_{z-} \end{vmatrix}$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{z-} = -\mathbf{u}_{z+}$, and $\{a_x, a_y, a_{z-}\}$ and $\{b_x, b_y, b_{z-}\}$ are respectively the components of **A** and **B** in the left-handed system.

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	Conventional	This paper's
Time Inversion	$B \rightarrow -B$	$E \leftrightarrow B$
Premise	Prime reality Matter ----- Field Secondary	Prime reality Field ----- Matter Secondary
Symmetry requirements	(Matter) Two kinds of monopoles (electric & magnetic) One kind of field (right-handed) (Field)	(Matter) One kind of monopole (electric = magnetic) Two kinds of field (right & left-handed) (Field)

Table I: Comparison between the conventional approach and this paper's.

Symmetrisation models			
	Conventional	This paper's	Salam's*
(Matter) Symmetry requirements	Two kinds of monopoles (electric & magnetic)	One kind of monopole (electric = magnetic)	Two kinds of monopoles (electric & magnetic)
(Field)	One kind of field (right-handed)	Two kinds of field (right & left-handed)	Two kinds of field* (handedness ,not defined)

Table II: Comparison between the conventional approach, Salam's and this paper's. In Salam's symmetrisation, the two types of field are presented as "electric" and "magnetic" photons, [13].

Figure 1: The circulation vector $d\vec{\ell}$, and the surface vectors $d\vec{S}_R$ and $d\vec{S}_L$, are defined according to the right or the left hand.

Figure 2: The two, t -forward and t -backward, waves, emerge at both sides of a time border with the opposite handedness. The t -forward wave is the conventional right-hand triad $E\mathbf{B}k$, and the t -backward wave, the corresponding *left-hand* triad. The symbols R and L stand for *right* and *left*, and represent the advance of a right- or left- screw.